

Synthesis of some New α, α' -Bis(3-nitro/aminobenzoyl)tellurium Dichlorides : A Search for Biologically Active Organotellurium Compounds

Y. D. KULKARNI*^a, ARCHNA RANI^a and R. A. SIDDIQUI^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

^bI. T. R. C., Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 30 December 1991, revised 6 May 1992, accepted 15 May 1992

Novel α, α' -bis(3-nitro/amino)benzoyltellurium dichlorides, their adducts with nitrogen donor molecules have been synthesised. The effect of these compounds on the levels of enzyme (Acetylcholine hydrolase) activity was studied against albino mice.

Biological activities of organotellurium compounds are well-known¹. Certain substituted diphenyl-tellurium dihalides and pseudohalides were found to show biocidal activity². However, the literature regarding the enzymatic approach to biocidal activity of these compounds is still scanty. Therefore, the present efforts were made and directed to synthesis of some novel α, α' -bis(3-substituted)-benzoyltellurium dichlorides to study the inhibition of AchE activity in cerebral cortex of albino mice.

Biological activity: The effect of organotellurium compounds (dose 500 mg/kg, i.p.) on the levels of acetylcholinesterase (AchE) activity after 24 h of administration is shown in Table 1. The activity of enzyme was determined according to method of Ellman³. The mortality in mice was recorded by the treatment of same compounds (600 mg/kg, i.p.), after 24 h in fasting conditions.

TABLE 1—BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	AchE activity* Mean \pm SE	LD ₅₀	Mortality %
1	3.5 \pm 2.7 ^a	>800	80
3	3.8 \pm 2.5	1000	60
4	1.6 \pm 1.9	1200	50
5	4.2 \pm 2.2	>1200	40
7	3.0 \pm 1.2	800	90
8	2.8 \pm 3.2	900	70
9	2.8 \pm 3.0	>900	70
Control	6.5 \pm 5.4		

*Expressed as mole of substrate hydrolysed per min per g \times 10⁻⁶.

^aValue is significantly different from value of control (p 0.001).

All the compounds screened for biological activity were found to be effective AchE inhibiting agents (Table 1). The results reveal that replacement of amino group (compound 4) by nitro group (1), and acetylamino (5) by diazo group (8 and 9) reduced the activity of parent compound.

Adduct with pyridine (3) was also found to be less effective than its precursor (1).

Experimental

All the solvents were purified by the standard methods⁴. Tellurium powder (200 mesh; B.D.H.) was used as such. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM 360L spectrometer. Tellurium was estimated volumetrically⁵.

M.ps. were recorded in open capillary tube and are uncorrected.

α, α' -Bis(3-nitrobenzoyl)tellurium dichloride (1): A mixture of 3-nitrobenzoyl chloride⁶ (5 g, 0.010 mol) and tellurium powder (0.63 g, 0.005 g-atom) was refluxed in dry benzene for 24 h. The product was extracted with benzene and crystallised with benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), (70%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 33.7; H, 1.58; N, 5.1; Te, 25.42. C₁₄H₈O₆N₂TeCl₂ requires: C, 33.73; H, 1.60; N, 5.6; Te, 25.59%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 450 (C–Te), 1520 (C–NO₂) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (CDCl₃) 2.0–3.22 (m, ArH).

Adduct formation with amine (2, 3): To 1 (0.5 g, 0.001 mol) in dichloromethane (10 ml), was added dropwise the appropriate amine (0.002 mol) in required quantity of dichloromethane. The mixture was refluxed for 36 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid was recrystallised from chloroform to yield the product, (2) (58%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 50.9; H, 4.3; N, 8.65; Te, 19.72. C₂₂H₃₀O₆N₄TeCl₂ requires: C, 40.93; H, 4.6; N, 8.68; Te, 19.79%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 480 (C–Te), 1700 (C=O), 3450 (NH sec), 1580 (NH bending) and 1060 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 3, (52%), m.p. 200°d (Found: C, 43.72; H, 2.70; N, 8.49; Te, 19.40. C₂₄H₁₈O₆N₄TeCl₂ requires: C 43.76; H, 2.73; N, 8.51; Te, 19.45%).

α, α' -Bis(3-aminobenzoyl)tellurium dichloride (4): Compound 1 was subjected to reduction by Raney Ni and hydrazine hydrate⁷ and the resulting solid

Scheme 1

crystallised from ethanol (the same compound was obtained by the direct synthesis from 3-aminobenzoyl chloride and elemental tellurium), (60%), m.p. 185° (Found : C, 26.01 ; H, 1.84 ; N, 4.30 ; Te, 29.09. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{TeCl}_2$ requires : C, 26.04 ; H, 1.86 ; N, 4.34 ; Te, 29.13%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 450 (C—Te), 1 650 (C=O), ~3 400 (NH), 1 590 (NH bending), 1 310 cm^{-1} (C—N).

Acetylation reaction get compound (5) was followed as follows. A mixture of compound 4 (0.005 mol) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (2 drops) was refluxed for ~ 24 h. Reaction mixture was then poured into water and

filtered. The resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform, (55%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 41.26 ; H, 3.02 ; N, 5.31 ; Te, 24.39. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{TeCl}_2$ requires : C, 41.30 ; H, 3.05 ; N, 5.35 ; Te, 24.46%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 540 (C—Te), 1 710 (C=O), 1 650 (C=O amide), 3 340 (NH) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (NH bending).

Schiff bases (6, 7) : A mixture of 4 (0.001 mol) in ethanol, concentrated H_2SO_4 (2 drops), sodium acetate (0.002 mol) and appropriate aldehyde was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The filtrate was concentrated to obtain the product : 6, (59%), m.p. 204° (Found : C, 54.59 ; H, 3.22 ; N, 4.52 ;

Te, 20.76. $C_{28}H_{80}O_2N_2TeCl_2$ requires : C, 54.63 ; H, 3.25 ; N, 4.55 ; Te, 20.79% ; 7, (43%), m.p. 193°d (Found : C, 47.61 ; H, 2.52 ; N, 7.89 ; Te, 19.14. $C_{28}H_{18}O_6N_4TeCl_2$ requires : C, 47.67 ; H, 2.55 ; N, 7.94 ; Te, 19.19%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 710 (C=O), 1 550 (C—NO₂) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=N).

α, α' -Bis-3-(4-substituted)phenylazobenzoyltellurium dichlorides (8—10) : To a solution of diazonium salt (0.001 mol) and sodium acetate (0.05 mol) cooled to 0—5°, was added the appropriate amine dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene : 8 (53%), m.p. 200°d (Found : C, 48.19 ; H, 3.04 ; N, 12.94 ; Te, 19.75. $C_{28}H_{90}O_2N_4TeCl_2$ requires : C, 48.22 ; H, 3.09 ; N, 12.98 ; Te, 19.78%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 500 (C—Te), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (N=N) ; 9 (52%), m.p. 181° (Found : C, 47.49 ; H, 3.35 ; N, 11.83 ; Te, 18.03. $C_{28}H_{24}O_4N_8TeCl_2$ requires : C, 47.52 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 11.88 ; Te, 18.10%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 480 (C—Te), 1 700 (C=O) and \sim 1 660 cm^{-1} (N=N) ; 10 (55%), m.p. 280° (Found : C, 49.75 ; H, 3.51 ; N, 12.39 ; Te, 18.91. $C_{28}H_{24}O_2N_8TeCl_2$ requires : C, 49.77 ; H, 3.55 ; N, 12.44 ; Te, 18.96%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) \sim 540 (C—Te), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (N=N).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., for spectral data and elemental analysis and grateful to Dr. S. Ray and Miss Versha Srivastava, C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

References

1. Y. D. KULKARNI, S. SRIVASTAVA and M. ATHAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 57 ; T. N. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. SRIVASTAVA, R. KUMAR, O. P. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. AWASTHI, *Bokin Bobai*, 1983, 11, 15 ; W. E. RUDZINSKI, T. M. AMINABHAVI, N. S. BIRADAR and C. S. PATIL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, 67, 177 ; G. T. MORGAN, E. A. COPPER and E. W. BRIT, *Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 190.
2. I. D. SADEKOV, I. A. BARCHAN, A. A. MAKSENENKO, B. B. RIVIKIN, M. L. CHERKINSKAYA E. L. SADEKOV, E. L. SIMKIN, YU. N. and V. I. MINKIN, *Khim. Pharm. Zh*, 1982, 16, 1073.
3. G. L. ELLMAN, K. D. COURTNEY, V. ANDRES, JR. and R. M. FEATHERSTONE, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1961, 7, 88.
4. "Vogel's Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry including qualitative Organic Analysis", eds. B. S. FURNISS, A. J. HONNAFORD, V. ROGERS, P. W. G. SMITH and A. R. TATCHELL, E.L.B.S., London, 1978, pp. 264-79, 689.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1975, p. 167.
6. J. B. COHEN, "Practical Organic Chemistry", MacMillan, London, 1949, p. 243.
7. Y. D. KULKARNI and S. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 65.